

QUIZ**LAST NAME: DESIR****FIRST NAME: RONALD****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **According to the ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1, you cannot write a successful essay unless you?**

- Use tables of contents and index to show relevant information.
- Give yourself enough time to read, research, think, and write.¹**
- Skim through the relevant text to locate specific information.
- Exercise critical thinking, which encourages you to broaden the focus.

2. **Which of the following is right about tables?**

- Notes that apply to the table as a whole are well numbered or lettered.
- The last note at the bottom of the table generally is set aside for reporting levels of probability.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 53.

- Each table should be labeled, ending with the table number and describing the contents.
- Chicago style tables may not use symbols in rows only in headings.

3. **Which of the following quotation changes are generally permissible?**

- The final period in a quote may be changed to a colon (and vice versa) to merge with your text.
- Double quotes can change to single quotes, and vice versa, for merging the quote with the rest of the text.³**
- Chicago style does not allow omission of reference citations in a quote.
- If a letter emphasizes a quote in the original, that letter should be changed to lowercase when run-in to your text and vice versa.

4. **Which statement is true about researchers?**

- The researchers' answer to a conceptual question is often not relevant to solving a practical problem.
- Experienced researchers are generally unafraid to consider any working hypothesis early in their project, especially ones they hold lightly.
- In most of the academic world, the primary aim of most researchers is to improve research.
- Researchers regularly think ahead to future steps.⁴**

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 49.

⁴ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 14.

5. **Which statement best describes a Ph.D. researcher?**
- Read generously to write a dissertation successfully.
 - Read generously to argue and defend your points.
 - Read generously to understand the materials on your terms critically.
 - Read generously to understand.⁵**
6. **Select the phrase that best expresses a relationship with the original expression "In drafting a report."**
- Use key terms to emphasize essential viewpoints.
 - Use key terms to explain better.
 - Use key terms to stop you from wandering.
 - Use a separate page for key terms.⁶**
7. **Moving from a topic to a question to a working hypothesis, it is unrealistic to:**
- Ask a question worth answering.
 - Anticipate the readers' questions of their own.
 - Find an answer that you can support for good reasons.
 - To believe all questions and answers are equally good.⁷**

⁵ Turabian, 30.

⁶ Turabian, 49.

⁷ Turabian, 16.

8. **Which answer least describes the role and writing of a Literature Review?**

- To determine that which done already.
- Emphasize a general form of writing.**⁸
- Consider the practice of argument in research.
- To think critically and consider the role of argument in research.

9. **Which is an objective of Petrie's thesis?**

- Provide an improved conceptualization of state sovereignty, the fundamental unit of analysis in international relations, international trade, and foreign economic policy.
- Provide an improved basis for describing and measuring the functioning of the inter-state system of governance.
- Define a new variable – jurisdictional integration - to measure the depth of international trade policy cooperation.
- Define conceptually coherent and distinct dimensions of this variable, to facilitate accurate measurement.**⁹

10. **Which question does not concern the Muendler dissertation?**

- How can economies benefit from globalization?
- Does foreign trade harm or foster growth?
- What role does information play in financial crises?

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (SAGE, 2008), 46.

⁹ Murray Campbell Petrie, "How Economic Globalisation Is Changing State Sovereignty" (PhD thesis, Victoria University of Wellington, 2009), 25.

- How can developed countries engage global markets on their terms?¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. SAGE, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Muendler, Marc-Andreas. "Essays on International Trade, Growth and Finance." PhD diss., University of California Berkeley, 2002.
- Petrie, Murray Campbell. "How Economic Globalisation Is Changing State Sovereignty." PhD thesis, Victoria University of Wellington, 2009.
- Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Marc-Andreas Muendler, "Essays on International Trade, Growth and Finance" (PhD diss., University of California Berkeley, 2002), 183.